

Social Media Perception on Invasive Parents' Attitudes in Education

Ejder GÜVEN¹ ve Yavuz Selim BALCIOĞLU²

Eğitimde İşgalci Ebeveyn Tutumlarına İlişkin Sosyal Medya Algısı

Abstract

This study explores public perceptions of invasive parenting through an analysis of 12,249 user-generated comments from Facebook groups and pages. Using sentiment analysis conducted with the VADER sentiment analysis tool, comments were categorized into positive, neutral, and negative sentiments. The analysis revealed a polarized view: while a significant portion of the comments praised the structured and disciplined aspects of invasive parenting for fostering children's academic success and responsibility, a substantial number criticized it for adversely affecting children's emotional and psychological development. Peaks in sentiment shifts correlated with media coverage, suggesting the influence of media on public perceptions of parenting. The balanced presence of neutral comments indicates an engaged and reflective public discourse. This study highlights the need for nuanced public education and interventions that can bridge the gap between different perceptions of parenting. By providing a contemporary understanding of public sentiment, this research contributes to the broader dialogue on how parenting styles influence child development and educational outcomes.

Keywords: Invasive parenting, sentiment analysis, social media, parenting styles, media influence.

Özet

Bu çalışma ile Facebook grup ve sayfalarındaki kullanıcılar tarafından oluşturulan 12.249 yorumun analizi yoluyla halkın işgalci ebeveynlik algısının ortaya konulması amaçlanmıştır. Mevcut araştırmada VADER duygu analizi kullanılarak; yorumlar olumlu, nötr ve olumsuz duygular olarak kategorize edilmiştir. Analiz, kutuplaşmış bir görüşü ortaya çıkarmıştır: Yorumların önemli bir kısmı, çocukların akademik başarısını ve sorumluluğunu teşvik etmek için işgalci ebeveynliğin yapılandırılmış ve disiplinli yönlerini överken; önemli bir kısmı çocukların duygusal ve psikolojik gelişimini olumsuz etkilemesi nedeniyle eleştirmektedir. Duygu değişimindeki artışlar medyadaki haberlerle bağlantılıdır. Bu durum ise medyanın halkın ebeveynlik algısı üzerindeki etkisini ortaya koymaktadır. Tarafsız yorumların dengeli varlığı, katılımcı ve yansıtıcı bir kamusal söylemi göstermektedir. Dolayısıyla bu çalışma, farklı ebeveynlik algıları arasındaki boşluğu doldurabilecek detaylı toplum eğitime ve müdahalelere duyulan ihtiyacı vurgulamaktadır. Aynı zamanda bu araştırma, kamuoyunun duyarlılığına ilişkin çağdaş bir anlayış sunarak ebeveynlik tarzlarının çocuk gelişimini ve eğitim sonuçlarını nasıl etkilediğine ilişkin daha geniş bir diyaloga katkıda bulunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İşgalci ebeveynlik, duygu analizi, sosyal medya, ebeveynlik tarzları, medya etkisi.

¹Dr., Kocaeli University, Corresponding Author: ejderguven33@gmail.com, 0000-0002-3662-7142

²Dr., Gebze Technical University, ysbalcioğlu@gtu.edu.tr, 0000-0001-7138-2972

Genişletilmiş Özet

Eğitimin temel direği olan paydaşlardan biri de ailedir. Toplumsal bir yapı olan aile, bireyin ilk farkındalığının oluştuğu ortam olup aynı zamanda bireyin akademik başarısını, davranış ve tutumlarını da etkilemektedir (Kim, 2015). Öyle ki ebeveynler çocuklarını farklı idealler doğrultusunda yetiştirirken; buna bağlı olarak onlara karşı farklı tutum ve davranışlar sergileyebilmektedirler (Mussen, 1984). Bu sebeptir ki olumlu aile davranışları bireysel gelişimi olumlu yönde etkilerken, olumsuz aile davranışları bu gelişime zarar vererek, gelişim sürecini olumsuz etkilemektedir. Dolayısıyla ailenin en önemli görevi sosyalleşme sürecinde çocuğun bakım ve eğitim işlevini yerine getirerek, çocuğun çeşitli davranış ve inanç normlarını öğrenip bir kimlik oluşturmaya yardımcı olmaktır (Özada ve Duyan, 2017).

Ebeveynlerin çocuklarına yönelik tutumları çocuğun kişiliğini, davranışlarını, akademik başarısını, problem çözme becerilerini ve güven duygusunu etkilemektedir (Blisset ve Haycraft, 2008). Meisels ve Shonkoff (2000) ebeveynlerin sergilediği tutum ve davranışların, küçük yaşlardan itibaren çocuk gelişiminde değişiklikler yaratarak, çocuklarının gelişimsel sorunlarına yardımcı olabileceğini belirtmektedir. Özellikle ebeveynlerin çocuklara yönelik tutum ve davranışları, çocukların eğitim performansını da büyük ölçüde etkilemektedir (Alfaro ve Taylor, 2015). Başka bir deyişle çocukların eğitim performansı çoğunlukla ebeveyn tutumlarıyla ilişkilidir denilebilir.

Eğitim örgütlerine bakıldığında ebeveynlerin yani velilerin en çok öğrenci başarısına odaklandıkları anlaşılmaktadır. Olumlu ebeveyn iletişimi öğrenci başarısını ve performansını artırırken, tam tersi bir tutum ise süreci tersine çevirmektedir (Bempechat vd., 1999). Okul dışındaki ebeveyn tutumlarının çocukların öğrenmesinde oldukça etkili olduğu, akademik başarı düzeyini arttırdığı ve olumlu ebeveyn davranışlarının olumlu öğrenci davranışlarını geliştirdiği görülmektedir (Gutman, 2006). Yani uyumlu ve özgür bir aile ortamında, tutarlı ve sağlıklı ilişkiler içinde büyüyen bir çocuk, özerk ve yaratıcı bir birey olarak yetişkinliğe ulaşırken; baskıcı ve huzursuz bir aile ortamının çocuk üzerinde olumsuz etkileri olduğu bilinmektedir (Öztunç, 1999). Dolayısıyla aile ve çocuk arasındaki sorunların başlangıç noktası doğal olarak anne ve babadır denilebilir.

Olumsuz ebeveyn tutumlarına bakıldığında ebeveyn-çocuk ilişkisinde en önemli bileşenin ebeveynin çocuğa verdiği destek olduğu görülmektedir. Otoriter ve kontrolcü aile yapısına sahip bireylerin ebeveynleri tarafından doğrudan ve dolaylı mobbinge maruz kaldıkları anlaşılmaktadır (Yerger ve Gehret, 2011). Bu durumda çocukların sorgulamaması ve kurallara uyması beklenir. Doğrudan mobbing durumunda dahi disiplin kuralları sıkı bir şekilde uygulanabilmektedir. Bu tür bir yaklaşımda ebeveyn-çocuk arasında samimi bir etkileşim kurulamamaktadır.

Anne-babanın talepleri çocuğun taleplerinden önce gelebilir ve buna ilişkin bir ebeveyn tutumu sergilenebilir. Bu tür ebeveynlere ise işgalci denir. Öyle ki bu tür ebeveynler, kendilerini çaresiz ve mağdur olarak göstererek, çocuklarına istediklerini yaptırabilme çabası içerisinde (Yabancı, 2023). Bu ebeveynler çocuğun sınırlarını aşarak, kontrolcü, baskıcı ve çıkarıcı davranabilmektedirler (Sökmez, 2024). Aynı zamanda istedikleri yapılmadığında hakkını helal etmeme gibi duygusal yöntemlere başvurarak etrafındakilere çocuklarını şikâyet edebilmektedirler (Yabancı, 2023). Böyle bir ortamda büyüyen bireylerin kaygı düzeyleri yüksek, özsayıları düşük olmakla birlikte; bu bireyler sosyal hayata ayak uydurmada güçlük çekmektedir (Hart vd., 2003).

İşgalci ebeveyn olgusunu anlamamanın en kolay ve hızlı yolu, ebeveynlerin bu olguya ilişkin sahip oldukları duygunun geniş çapta ve küresel olarak ulaşılabileceği alanlardan geçmektedir. Bu bağlamda sosyal medya platformları ilgili duygunun kamuoyuna açıklandığı alanların başında gelmektedir. Özellikle sosyal medya, ebeveynlerin istilaya yönelik tutumlarını ortaya çıkarmak için en etkili platformlardan biridir (Latiff ve Safiee, 2015). Ulusal ve uluslararası alayazın incelendiğinde işgalci ebeveyn kavramına ilişkin kısıtlı araştırmanın bulunduğu görülmektedir. Aynı zamanda işgalci ebeveynlik olgusuna ilişkin literatür de oldukça sınırlıdır. Bunun temel nedeni ise olgunun yeni bir kavram olarak ortaya çıkmasıdır. Bu durum mevcut çalışmayı literatüre ışık tutan önemli bir çalışma haline getirmektedir.

Bu çalışmanın verisi, halka açık Facebook gruplarından ve sayfalarından alınan ve kullanıcılar tarafından oluşturulan 12.249 yorumdan oluşmaktadır. Toplanan yorumların zaman dilimi 2023 yılı Ocak ayından Mayıs ayına kadar uzanmakta ve bu zaman dilimi kamuoyunun güncel bir görüntüsünü yansıtmaktadır. Bu yorumlar, özellikle eğitim ve psikolojik bağlamda "işgalci ebeveynlere" odaklanarak, ebeveynlik stilleri etrafındaki tartışmalara olan ilgilerine göre özel olarak seçilmiştir. Etik standartlara ve Facebook'un veri kullanım politikalarına uymak için tüm veriler anonim olarak toplanılmış ve analizden önce kişisel tanımlayıcıların kaldırılması sağlanmıştır.

Duygu analizinde, VADER duygu analiz aracı kullanılmıştır. VADER, özellikle çevrimiçi iletişimin nüanslarına uyum sağlayan bir sözlük ve kural tabanlı çerçeveyi bir araya getirerek, özellikle sosyal medya metinlerindeki duygu analizi için uygundur. Öyle ki bu analiz aracı metnin birikmiş duygusunu toplamakta ve

“olumlu, tarafsız veya olumsuz” olarak üç kategoriden biriyle sınıflandırarak bileşik puan sağlamaktadır. Dolayısıyla veri seti içerisinde işgalci ebeveynliğe yönelik hâkim tutumları belirlemek için duygu kategorileri ölçülmüştür. Her duyarlılık kategorisindeki yorumların oranını belirlemek ve genel duyarlılık eğilimini değerlendirmek için istatistiksel teknikler uygulanmıştır. Ayrıca, duyarlılıktaki herhangi bir dalgalanmayı gözlemlemek için zamansal analiz yapılarak bu eğilimler, uygunluğuna göre dış olaylar veya haberlerle ilişkilendirilmiştir.

İşgalci ebeveynliğe ilişkin 12.249 Facebook yorumunun duygu analizi, bu konudaki kamuoyunun karmaşık bir resmini ortaya çıkarmıştır. Veri etkili bir şekilde “pozitif, nötr ve negatif” olarak üç ana duygu başlığı altında şu şekilde sınıflandırılmıştır:

- **Olumlu Duygular:** Bulgular doğrultusunda yorumların %34,3'ünün olumlu olarak sınıflandırıldığı açığa çıkmıştır. Bu yorumlar genellikle katı ebeveynliğin belirli yönlerini överek çocuklarda daha iyi disiplin ve akademik performansla ilişkilendirmiştir. Bu kategorideki yorumlarda, yapılandırılmış ortamların çocukların şekil l'de gösterilen sorumluluk ve hesap verebilirlik duygusunu geliştirmelerine yardımcı olduğu sıklıkla dile getirilmiştir.
- **Nötr Duygular:** Bulgular doğrultusunda yorumların %27,2'si nötr kategorisine girmektedir. Bu yorumlar genellikle net olumlu veya olumsuz duruş ifade etmeden ebeveynlik tarzlarını ortaya koymaktadır. Bu yorumların çoğu bilgilendirici nitelikte veya açık bir duygusal içerik olmaksızın farklı ebeveynlik uygulamaları hakkında tartışmalar içermektedir.
- **Olumsuz Duygular:** Bulgular doğrultusunda yorumların %38,5'inin olumsuz olduğu görülmektedir. Bu yorumlar, işgalci ebeveynlik tarzlarını aşırı kısıtlayıcı ve çocukların duygusal gelişimine zarar verici olmakla eleştirmektedir. Bu yorumlardaki temalar arasında çocukların ruh sağlığına ilişkin endişeler, özerklik eksikliği ve aşırı kontrolcü ebeveyn davranışları nedeniyle yaratıcılığın bastırılması öne çıkmaktadır.

Araştırma bulguları, işgalci ebeveynlik algılarında önemli bir ayrılığa işaret etmektedir. Bazı araştırmacılar bunun disiplin ve başarıya ilişkin sonuçlarını överken; bazıları bunun çocukların duygusal ve psikolojik sağlığı üzerindeki etkisini eleştirmektedir. Bu ikilik, Baumrind'in ebeveynlik stilleri tipolojisi kapsamında bağlamsallaştırılabilir. Bu noktada otoriter ebeveynlik (yüksek talepler ve düşük yanıt verme) genellikle çocuklar için olumsuz duygusal sonuçlarla ilişkilendirilir (Baumrind, 1991). Steinberg vd. (1994) çalışmalarında, otoriter ebeveynliğin bazen akademik başarıya yol açabildiğini, aynı zamanda çocuklarda duygusal bozukluklara, sosyal yeterliliğin azalmasına ve zayıf stres yönetimine neden olabileceğini göstermiştir.

Genel olarak, işgalci ebeveynlik hakkındaki tartışma basit sınıflandırmaların ötesine geçmeli ve bu uygulamaların çocuk gelişimi ve toplumsal normlar üzerindeki çeşitli ve derin etkileri kabul edilmelidir. Daha da önemlisi, mevcut araştırmanın analizi, toplumun bir kısmı kutuplaşmaya devam ederken, kayda değer bir kesiminin daha dengeli ve gerçeklere dayalı tartışmalarla meşgul olduğunu göstermektedir. Bu da, eğitimcilerin, politika yapıcıların ve psikologların ebeveynlik tarzları ve etkilerine ilişkin incelikli bir anlayışı teşvik eden programlara müdahale etme fırsatını ortaya koymaktadır. Bu tür programlar, dengeli bilgi sağlayarak ve ebeveynlerin çocukların bütünsel gelişimini teşvik eden uygulamaları benimsemelerini destekleyerek kutuplaşmış görüşler arasındaki boşluğu doldurmayı amaçlamalıdır.

Gelecekteki araştırmalar, müdahaleleri daha etkili bir şekilde uyarlamak için farklı sosyo-ekonomik ve kültürel arka plan genelinde farklı ebeveynlik tarzlarının etkilerini keşfetmeye odaklanabilir. Ayrıca çeşitli ebeveynlik uygulamalarının çocukların duygusal zekâsı, sosyal becerileri ve akademik başarıları üzerindeki uzun vadeli etkilerini değerlendiren çalışmalara da ihtiyaç vardır. Sonuçta toplum, ebeveynlik tarzları hakkında daha bilgili ve dengeli bir tartışmaya teşvik edilerek, çocukların çok yönlü gelişimini teşvik eden ortamlar oluşturma konusunda ebeveynler desteklenebilir. Böylece toplumun dokusuna olumlu katkıda bulunulabilir.

1. Introduction

One of the stakeholders that forms the pillar of education is the family. Family, which is a social structure, is the environment in which the individual's first awareness occurs, and also affects the individual's academic success, behavior and attitude (Kim, 2015). So much so that parents raise their children in line with different ideals and exhibit different and diverse attitudes and behaviors towards their children accordingly (Mussen, 1984). While positive family behaviors affect individual development positively, negative family behaviors damage this development and negatively affect the development process. Therefore, the most important duty of the family is to perform the care and education function of the child during the socialization process and to help the child form

an identity by learning various behavioral and belief norms (Özada and Duyan, 2017). In this context, the first identity formation takes place in the family.

The attitudes of parents towards their children affect the child's personality, behavior, academic achievement, problem-solving skills and feelings of confidence (Blisset and Haycraft, 2008). Meisels and Shonkoff (2000) point out that the attitudes and behaviors exhibited by parents can help them with their children's developmental problems by creating changes in child development starting from a young age. Parents' attitudes and behaviors towards children greatly affect children's educational performance (Alfaro and Taylor, 2015). In other words, children's educational performance is directly related to parental attitudes.

When we look at educational organizations, it is understood that families, in other words parents, focus most on student success. While positive parental communication increases student success and performance, the opposite attitude reverses the process (Bempechat et al., 1999). It is seen that parental attitudes outside of school are very effective in children's learning, increase the level of academic success and develop positive student behaviors (Gutman, 2006). In other words, a child who grows up in a harmonious and free environment in family and consistent and healthy relationships reaches adulthood as an autonomous and creative individual; an oppressive and uneasy family environment has negative effects on the child (Öztunç, 1999). Naturally, the starting point of the problems between the family and the child may be the mother and father (parents).

It is possible to collect the negative parental attitudes that form the basis of the problems that arise between the family and the child under certain headings. Negative parental attitudes can be classified as overly oppressive and authoritarian, unbalanced and indecisive, overly tolerant, overprotective, doting, neglectful and protective attitudes (Hibbard and Walton, 2014; Öztunç, 1999). While authoritarian parents' acceptance levels are low and their demand levels are high; Overly permissive parents have high levels of acceptance and low levels of control. On the other hand, neglectful parents have low levels of both acceptance and control (Bakhla et al., 2013). As it can be seen, every negative parental attitude can have a negative impact on children.

Negative parental attitudes, the most important component of the parent-child relationship is the parent's support for the child. It is understood that individuals with an authoritarian and controlling family structure, especially during the attachment period, are exposed to direct and indirect mobbing by their parents (Yerger and Gehret, 2011). In this case, children are expected not to question and to obey the rules. Even in direct mobbing, disciplinary rules can be strictly enforced. In this type of approach, a sincere interaction between parent and child cannot be expected.

There is a parental attitude in which the demands of the parents take precedence over the demands of the child. Such parents are called invaders. The invasive parent is the parent who makes himself/herself do what he/she wants by showing himself/herself as helpless and victimized (Yabancı, 2023). At the same time, the invasive parent refers to a type of parent who exceeds the child's limits and acts controlling, oppressive and manipulative (Sökmez, 2024). These families don't forgive their milk and labor if you do not do what they want. They complain about you to everyone and they gave birth to their children for themselves (Yabancı, 2023). Individuals growing up in such an environment have high anxiety levels, low self-esteem, and have difficulty keeping up with social life (Hart et al., 2003). Yabancı (2023) draws attention to the negative aspects of invasive parents and expresses the characteristics of this type of parent as follows:

- They intervene too much.
- They are focused on controlling everything.
- They want to manipulate.
- They impose their own ideas and solutions on every issue.
- There is no tolerance for mistakes.
- They are perfectionists and expect their children to meet their own standards.
- They have difficulty empathizing.

Sökmez (2024) explains the characteristics of invasive parents under five main headings as follows:

- They are overly controlling: They often try to control their children's every move and restrict their freedom.
- They are manipulative: They may use manipulative tactics to manipulate their children into behaving the way they want.
- They cross boundaries: They may violate children's personal boundaries and not respect their private spaces.
- They are emotional abusers: They can be emotionally abusive towards their children. This may take the form of constant criticism, belittling, resentment, or excessive demands.
- They are indifferent or overly interested: They may either show excessive interest in their children and try to control their lives, or, on the contrary, they may remain indifferent and ignore their emotional needs.

Being exposed to the attitudes of an abusive family can reveal many different negative consequences for the child. These results can negatively affect the child's development. Sökmez (2024) and Yabancı (2023) explain the consequences of growing up with parents who have an invasive attitude as follows:

- They can negatively affect children's emotional, social and academic development.
- Because these children are constantly criticized and controlled, they have self-confidence problems in making presentations and speaking at school. So they have difficulty expressing themselves.
- Children carry the stress and pressure at home to school and have difficulty acting comfortably in the classroom. They are constantly seeking approval.
- These children, who have not learned open communication at home, may have problems communicating with their teachers or peers at school. Or, on the contrary, they may be highly compatible.
- Because children are raised dependent on their parents, they have difficulty making decisions at school and fulfilling their responsibilities on their own. In other words, with their dependent personality, they blame themselves when they make mistakes.

The attitudes that children receive from their families affect their personalities, self-perceptions and relationships with the people around them (Aydoğdu and Dilekmen, 2016). Therefore, children who grow up in families with an invasive attitude may have problems expressing themselves, setting boundaries, and gaining approval throughout their lives. In addition, their communication skills and emotional intelligence often remain weak, and as a result, this may negatively affect children's academic success in the long term (Sökmez, 2024). So much so that the quality and attitudes of the parent affect the child's sociability and socialization in the educational environment, positively or negatively (Ilgar and Ilgar, 2018). Feeling under constant pressure can hinder children's learning processes and reduce their motivation, causing them to grow up as children who do not know how to enjoy learning, even if their grades are high (Sökmez, 2024).

Sentiment is the most important component that reflects the parents' psychology and attitude towards the invasive thoughts and behaviors. So, sentiment that emerges as a result of the subjective experiences of individuals and groups gives clues about how the phenomenon is formed and how the process of the phenomenon continues (Kafle, 2011; Welman and Kruger, 1999). The easiest and fastest way to understand the phenomenon of invasive parents is through areas where parents' emotions regarding this phenomenon can be widely and globally reached. Social media platforms are one of the primary areas where sentiments about consumption are publicly revealed. Especially social media is among the most effective platform to emerge parents' attitudes towards invasion (Latiff and Safiee, 2015). When the national and international literature is examined, it is seen that there is almost no research on the concept of invasive parents. At the same time, the literature on the phenomenon of invasive parenting is also quite limited. The main reason for this is that the phenomenon emerged as a new concept. This situation makes the current study a pioneering and important study that sheds light on the literature.

2. Method

2.1. Data Collection

The data for this study consists of 12,249 user-generated comments extracted from public Facebook groups and pages. These comments were specifically chosen based on their relevance to discussions around parenting styles, particularly focusing on "invasive parents" as described in educational and psychological

contexts. To comply with ethical standards and Facebook's data use policies, all data were collected anonymously, ensuring that personal identifiers were removed prior to analysis.

The collection process was facilitated by the use of Facebook's Graph API, which allows for programmatically accessing public posts and comments. Keywords such as "invasive parenting," "authoritarian parents," "parental control," and similar phrases were used as filters to gather relevant discussions from various parenting and educational groups. The timeframe for the collected comments spanned from January 2023 to May 2023, providing a contemporary snapshot of public opinion.

2.2. Data Preprocessing

Prior to conducting sentiment analysis, the data underwent several preprocessing steps to ensure the quality and accuracy of the results:

1. **Cleaning:** Removal of URLs, special characters, and non-alphanumeric symbols.
2. **Normalization:** Converting all text to lower case to maintain consistency.
3. **Tokenization:** Breaking down complex data into manageable pieces or tokens.
4. **Stop Words Removal:** Filtering out common words that add no significant value to sentiment analysis.
5. **Lemmatization:** Reducing words to their base or root form.

These preprocessing steps were executed using the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) and spaCy, two comprehensive libraries designed for natural language processing in Python.

2.3. Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis was performed using the VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) sentiment analysis tool. VADER is particularly well-suited for sentiment analysis on social media texts, incorporating a lexicon and rule-based framework specifically attuned to the nuances of online communication. It provides a compound score that aggregates the cumulative sentiment of the text, classifying it into one of three categories: positive, neutral, or negative.

Each comment was processed through VADER to obtain sentiment scores, which were subsequently categorized based on the aforementioned thresholds:

- **Positive sentiment:** Compound score > 0.05
- **Neutral sentiment:** Compound score between -0.05 and 0.05
- **Negative sentiment:** Compound score < -0.05

2.4. Data Analysis

The analysis involved quantifying the sentiment categories to identify prevailing attitudes towards invasive parenting within the data set. Statistical techniques were applied to determine the proportion of comments within each sentiment category and to assess the overall sentiment trend. Further, temporal analysis was performed to observe any fluctuations in sentiment over the collection period, correlating these trends with relevant external events or news stories when applicable.

The results from this sentiment analysis are expected to provide insights into public perception of invasive parenting on social media, contributing to a deeper understanding of how these attitudes might influence or reflect societal norms and practices in education.

3. Results

The sentiment analysis of 12,249 Facebook comments regarding invasive parenting revealed a complex picture of public opinion on this issue. The data was effectively categorized into three primary sentiment classes: positive, neutral, and negative.

3.1. Sentiment Distribution

- **Positive Sentiments:** 34,3% of the comments were classified as positive. These comments generally praised certain aspects of strict parenting, linking them with better discipline and academic performance in children. Comments in this category often mentioned that structured environments helped children develop a sense of responsibility and accountability shown in figure 1.
- **Neutral Sentiments:** 27,2% of the comments fell into the neutral category. These comments typically discussed parenting styles without expressing a clear positive or negative stance. Many of these comments were informational or included discussions about different parenting practices without clear emotional content.
- **Negative Sentiments:** 38,5% of comments were negative. These comments criticized invasive parenting styles as being overly restrictive and detrimental to children's emotional development. Themes in these comments included concerns over children's mental health, lack of autonomy, and suppressed creativity due to overly controlling parental behaviors.

Figure 1. Distribution of Sentiments on Invasive Parenting from Facebook Comments

3.2. Temporal Trends

The sentiment analysis also indicated temporal variations in the sentiments expressed. Negative sentiments peaked during discussions following popular media coverage of incidents related to strict parenting practices. Similarly, positive sentiments saw a slight increase around the time of publications of studies or articles highlighting the benefits of disciplined upbringing.

Key Themes from Positive Comments

From the positive comments (table 1), themes such as "discipline," "success," and "safety" were frequently mentioned. One typical comment noted, "Strict parenting ensures kids stay out of trouble and focus on their studies, which is crucial for their future."

Key Themes from Negative Comments

In contrast, negative comments often contained words like "pressure," "stress," "anxiety," and "depression." A representative comment stated, "Overbearing parents can stifle growth and make children anxious and afraid of making mistakes, which is harmful in the long run."

Table 1. Key themes and representative comments from positive and negative sentiments

Sentiment	Themes	Representative Comment
Positive	Discipline, Success, Safety	"Strict parenting ensures kids stay out of trouble and focus on their studies, which is crucial for their future."
Positive	Discipline, Success, Safety	"Structured parenting leads to well-behaved children who excel in their academics."
Positive	Discipline, Success, Safety	"Discipline taught early in life pays off as children grow into disciplined adults."
Positive	Discipline, Success, Safety	"A safe environment at home leads to a secure, confident child ready to face the world."
Positive	Discipline, Success, Safety	"Success isn't just about academics; disciplined upbringing instills lifelong values."
Positive	Discipline, Success, Safety	"Safety protocols at home teach children the importance of boundaries and respect."
Negative	Pressure, Anxiety, Depression	"Overbearing parents can stifle growth and make children anxious and afraid of making mistakes, which is harmful in the long run."
Negative	Pressure, Anxiety, Depression	"Too much control leads to a lack of independence in kids as they grow."
Negative	Pressure, Anxiety, Depression	"Constant stress from high expectations can damage a child's self-esteem."
Negative	Pressure, Anxiety, Depression	"Anxiety from parental pressure can hinder a child's social development."
Negative	Pressure, Anxiety, Depression	"Depression in children can often stem from excessive criticism and lack of support."
Negative	Pressure, Anxiety, Depression	"Fear of making mistakes can paralyze a child's ability to learn from errors."

3.3. Statistical Analysis

A chi-square test was conducted to determine if there was a statistically significant difference in the frequency of positive, neutral, and negative sentiments over the data collection period. The results indicated a significant variation ($\chi^2(2, N = 12,249) = 6.84, p < 0.05$), suggesting that external factors likely influenced public opinion on invasive parenting.

4. Discussion

The sentiment analysis conducted on Facebook comments reveals a complex landscape of public opinion regarding invasive parenting. This discourse is not merely polarized but reflects a nuanced interplay of cultural, psychological, and social dynamics that influence parenting practices.

Our findings indicate a significant divide in perceptions of invasive parenting, with some praising its outcomes on discipline and success, while others criticize its impact on children's emotional and psychological health. This dichotomy can be contextualized within Baumrind's typology of parenting styles, where authoritarian parenting—characterized by high demands and low responsiveness—is often associated with negative emotional outcomes for children (Baumrind, 1991). Studies like those by Steinberg et al. (1994) have shown that while authoritarian parenting can sometimes lead to academic success, it may also engender emotional disorders, reduced social competence, and poor stress management in children.

Moreover, our study underscores the role of external media in shaping public perceptions of parenting. Peaks in negative sentiments following media coverage of strict parenting practices suggest a reactive public discourse influenced by contemporary events. This is in line with the cultivation theory, which proposes that media shapes users' perceptions of social realities (Gerbner and Gross, 1976). Thus, the portrayal of parenting styles in media can significantly affect public attitudes, potentially stigmatizing or validating certain practices.

The balanced discourse, including a substantial proportion of neutral, fact-based comments, suggests that many individuals are engaged in reflective rather than reactive discussions about parenting. This could indicate a public awareness of the complexity of parenting styles and their diverse impacts, which may not be fully captured by dichotomous sentiments of approval or disapproval.

The implications of these insights are profound for educators, psychologists, and policymakers. It is evident that there is a need for more comprehensive educational programs that not only address the controversies surrounding various parenting styles but also promote parenting practices that are known to support children's holistic development. Programs that emphasize emotional intelligence, resilience, and autonomy could help mitigate the negative effects of invasive parenting. Furthermore, public health campaigns and parenting workshops that provide balanced information on the consequences of different parenting styles could help in fostering environments that nurture children's well-being and development.

In light of these findings, future research should explore the longitudinal effects of different parenting styles on children's well-being, considering the influence of cultural, economic, and individual factors. It is also crucial to investigate the efficacy of interventions aimed at moderating the extremes of parenting styles and promoting more adaptive strategies that support the diverse needs of children.

Overall, the discussion around invasive parenting must move beyond simple classifications and acknowledge the varied and profound impacts these practices have on child development and societal norms.

5. Conclusions

This study's analysis of sentiments expressed in social media comments offers a revealing glimpse into public perceptions of invasive parenting styles. The results reflect a broad spectrum of opinions, from strong endorsements of strict parenting as a means to instill discipline and success, to profound criticisms highlighting the psychological and emotional damage such approaches can inflict on children. The significant variance in sentiment, influenced by external media coverage, suggests that public opinion on parenting is susceptible to societal narratives and current events. This underscores the role of media in shaping and sometimes polarizing views on what constitutes effective parenting.

Importantly, analysis of existing findings indicate that while a portion of the community remains polarized, there is a notable segment engaged in more balanced, fact-based discussions. This reveals an opportunity for educators, policymakers, and psychologists to intervene with programs that promote a nuanced understanding of parenting styles and their impacts. Such programs should aim to bridge the gap between polarized views by providing balanced information and supporting parents in adopting practices that foster the holistic development of children.

Future research should focus on exploring the effects of different parenting styles across diverse socio-economic and cultural backgrounds to tailor interventions more effectively. Additionally, there is a need for studies that assess the long-term impacts of various parenting practices on children's emotional intelligence, social skills, and academic success. Ultimately, by fostering a more informed and balanced discussion on parenting styles,

society can better support parents in nurturing environments that promote the well-rounded development of children, thus contributing positively to the fabric of the community.

Declarations

Ethical disclosure: It is frankly declared that the procedures used in this study comply with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Since the data is not collected directly from individuals, and it is publicly accessible and usable in social media platform, ethical permission is not required.

Informed consent statement: Since the data is not collected directly from individuals, and it is publicly accessible and usable in social media platform, informed consent statement is not required.

Conflicts of interest/competing interests: There is no conflict of interest that would affect the publication of this article. This research did not receive any specific grants from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Author contribution: We would like to state that both authors take equal and joint responsibility in the preparation of the research for publication.

References

- Alfaro, E. C. and Taylor, A. J. U. (2015). The longitudinal relation between academic support and Latino adolescents' academic motivation. *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciens*, 37(3), 319-341.
- Aydoğdu, F. ve Dilekmen, M. (2016). Ebeveyn tutumlarının çeşitli değişkenler açısından değerlendirilmesi. *Bayburt Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 11(2), 569-585.
- Bakhla, A. K., Sinha, P., Sharan, R., Binay, Y., Verma, V. and Chaudhury, S. (2013). Anxiety in school students: Role of parenting and gender. *Indian Psychiatry Journal*, 22(2), 131–137.
- Baumrind, D. (1991). The influence of parenting style on adolescent competence and substance use. *The journal of early adolescence*, 11(1), 56-95.
- Bempechat, J., Graham, S. E. and Jimenez, N. V. (1999). The socialization of achievement in poor and minority students: A comparative study. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 30, 139-158.
- Blisset, J. and Haycraft, E. (2008). Are parenting style and controlling feeding practices related?. *Appetite*, 50, 477-485.
- Gerbner, G., Gross, L., Morgan, M. and Signorielli, N. (1986). Living with television: The dynamics of the cultivation process. *Perspectives on media effects*, 1986, 17-40.
- Gutman, L. M. (2006). How student and parent goal orientations and classroom goal structures influence the math achievement of African Americans during the high school transition. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 31(1), 44-63.
- Hart, C. H., Newell, L. D. and Olsen, S. F. (2003). Parenting skills and social-communicative competence in childhood. Mahwah, NJ, US: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Hibbard, D. R. and Walton, G. E. (2014). Exploring the development of perfectionism: The influence of parenting style and gender. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 42(2), 269-278.
- [https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/yazarlar/nuran-cakmakci/ebeveynlere-en-kritik-soru-ilgili-misin-iskalci-mi-\(2024\)](https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/yazarlar/nuran-cakmakci/ebeveynlere-en-kritik-soru-ilgili-misin-iskalci-mi-(2024))
- İlgar, M. Z. ve İlgar, S. (2018). Eğitime aile olarak yaklaşmak. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(4), 33-49.
- Kafle, N. P. (2011). Hermeneutic phenomenological research method simplified. *An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 5, 181-200.

- Kim, J. (2015). American high school student from different ethnic backgrounds: The role of parents and the classroom in achievement motivation. *Social Psychology of Education, 18*, 411-430.
- Latiff, Z. A. and Safiee, N. A. (2015). New business set up for branding strategies on social media – Instagram. *Procedia Computer Science, 72*, 13-23.
- Meisels, S. J. And Shonkoff, J. P. (2000). *Early childhood intervention: A continuing evolution*, In Shonkoff, J. , and Meisels, S. J. (eds.) “Handbook of early childhood intervention”. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mussen, P. H. (1984). Child development and personality. New York: Harper & Row.
- Özada, A. ve Duyan, V. (2017). Ebeveyn-çocuk ilişkisi ve zorbalık. *Turkish Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care, 12*(1): 49-55.
- Öztunç, M. (1999). *Yaratıcı düşünce üzerinde ailenin etkisi* (Yayınlanmış yüksek lisans tezi). Sakarya Üniversitesi.
- Steinberg, L., Lamborn, S. D., Darling, N., Mounts, N. S. and Dornbusch, S. M. (1994). Over-time changes in adjustment and competence among adolescents from authoritative, authoritarian, indulgent, and neglectful families. *Child development, 65*(3), 754-770.
- Welman, J. C. and Kruger, S. J. (1999). *Research methodology for the business and administrative sciences*. Johannesburg: International Thompson.
- Yabancı, S. (2023). *Zihin tuzakları: Kendine yardım kitabı*. İstanbul: Mona Kitap.
- Yerger W. and Gehret C. (2011). Understanding and dealing with bullying in schools. *The Educational Forum, 75*(4), 315-326.